

Research paper

SMART FIRE DETECTION AND ALERT SYSTEM USING GSM AND MULTI SENSOR TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Fire accidents are one of the major causes of loss of human life, environmental devastation, and property damage across public and industrial areas. Traditional fire alarm system mainly depends on local alarms manual checks, which may delay emergency alerts during critical incidents. To overcome this problem this paper presents a smart fire Detection and Alert System using Arduino UNO, MQ-2 sensor, flame sensor, and A7670c SIM module.

The proposed system continuously monitors real time environmental data, including smoke detection and flame intensity. The MQ-2 sensor detects smoke and harmful gases while flame sensor identifies the presence of fire. Whenever abnormal conditions are detected, the Arduino UNO processes sensor data and activities the alert process. The A7670C SIM module immediately sends emergency SMS or call alerts to the user for quick response

The system is powered using a 12V 2A adapter, while a buck converter provides stable voltage regulation for safe operation of electronic components. The project aims to provide a low-cost, reliable and efficient fire safety solution suitable for homes, laboratories, offices, industries, warehouses, and commercial buildings.

Our proposed system advances fire safety by prioritizing early detection and rapid communication. To ensure real-world viability, we focused on creating a solution that is as economically efficient and easy to deploy.

Keywords- Fire Detection system, Arduino UNO, MQ-2 Sensor, Flame Sensor, GSM Alert System, Embedded Systems, Smart System, Real-Time Monitoring.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fire accidents are increasing at an accelerated space in residential, industrial, and commercial environments due to electrical faults, gas leakage,

overheating equipment, flammable materials, and human negligence. In many situations, delayed fire detection causes severe loss of life and property damage. Therefore, there is a strong need for

intelligent fire detection systems capable of providing immediate warning and emergency communication.

Traditional fire safety systems mainly depend on smoke alarms and manual observation. Such system only provides local alerts and requires human presence for monitoring. In crowded or unattended areas, fire incidents may remain unnoticed during the initial stage.

Modern embedded systems and sensor technologies provide better solutions for fire monitoring and emergency communication. The proposed Smart Fire Detection and Alert system use Arduino UNO as the main controller along with MQ-2 Smoke Sensor and flame sensor for environmental monitoring.

Whenever smoke or flame is detected, the Arduino UNO processes the sensor values and activates the A7670C SIM module to send emergency SMS or call alerts to the user. This fast communication mechanism improves emergency response time and reduces fire related damage.

Fig. 1: Hardware components used in system

The project focused on:

- Early detection

- Smoke and flame monitoring
- GSM-based alerts
- Low cost
- Reliable safety system
- Easy installation and maintenance

The proposed system can be used in homes, offices, industries, warehouses, laboratories, shopping malls, data centers and smart safety applications.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Many researchers have developed fire detection system using different sensing and communication technologies. Traditional fire alarms systems mainly use just one sensor.

This type systems are widely used, but they suffer from several drawbacks including delayed response, lack of remote monitoring, and high human dependency.

Earlier systems used standalone smoke sensors that only generated local alarms.

Later, GSM-based systems are introduced to send emergency SMS alerts during fire accidents.

These systems improved communication capability but depends on single sensor monitoring.

Modern smart safety integrates multiple sensors such as smoke sensors, flame sensors, and temperature sensors to improve detection accuracy.

Embedded controllers like Arduino UNO

Provides flexible programing and sensor interfacing capabilities.

Researchers have also implemented IoT-based fire monitoring systems using Wi-Fi communication.

However, such systems require stable internet connectivity.

GSM-based systems provide more reliable communication in areas where internet access may not be available.

The proposed system improves upon existing methods by integrating:

- MQ-2 smoke sensor
- Flame sensor
- Arduino UNO controller
- A760C SIM communication module
- Stable power regulation using buck converter
- Instant SMS and call alerts

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Many existing fire safeties fail to provide immediate intelligence response during emergencies. Traditional systems mainly depends on local alarms, which may not be effective in unattended areas.

Major problems are:

- 1) Delay in detection of fire
- 2) Lack of immediate communication
- 3) Human dependency
- 4) Increased property damage
- 5) Safety risks
- 6) Limited monitoring capability
- 7) High cost of advanced commercial system

To overcome these issues, a low-cost smart fire detection system with automatic GSM alert capability system is required.

4. OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of the project are:

- 1) To design a Smart fire detection system using Arduino UNO.
- 2) To detect smoke and fire using MQ-2 and flame sensor.
- 3) To give automatic emergency alert using GSM technology.
- 4) To improve fire safety and emergency response.
- 5) To reduce fire-related damage and accidents.
- 6) To develop a low-cost and efficient safety system.
- 7) To create a reliable monitoring solution for homes and industries.

5. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed system uses MQ-2 smoke sensor and flame sensor connected to the Arduino UNO controller. The sensor continuously monitor environmental situations and send data to the controller.

5.1. Working Methodology

1. MQ-2 sensor continuously monitors smoke and gas levels.
2. Flame sensor detects fire or infrared flame intensity.
3. Arduino UNO processes sensor data continuously.
4. Threshold values are predefined in the program.
5. If smoke or fire exceeds safety limits:
 - Alert condition becomes active.
 - GSM communication starts.
 - Emergency SMS/call alert is sent.

5.2. System features

- Real-time smoke detection
- Fire sensing capability
- GSM-based emergency communication
- Stable power supply system
- Low-cost implementation
- Reliable operation

6. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 2: Circuit diagram of proposed system

7. HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

Component	Quantity	Purpose	Approx. Cost (INR)
Arduino UNO	1	Main Controller	550
MQ-2 Sensor	1	Smoke/Gas Detection	230
Flame Sensor	1	Fire Detection	150
A7670C SIM Module	1	SMS/Call Alert Communication	900

Buck Converter	1	Voltage Regulation	80
12V 2A Adapter	1	Power Supply	250
Connecting Wires	1 Set	Circuit Connections	50

Total Estimation Cost: Approximate Project cost: 2200-2500 rupees

7.1 SENSOR SPECIFICATION

Sensors	Operating voltage	Function	Detection Capability
MQ-2 Sensor	5V	Smoke/Gas detection	LPG, Smoke, Methane

Flame Sensor	3.3V-5V	Fire detection	Infrared Flame
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7.2 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS

Software	Purpose
Arduino IDE	Program development
Embedded C	Coding language
Serial Monitor	Monitoring Sensor Data
GSM Libraries	SIM Communication

The Arduino IDE is used for writing, Compiling, and uploading the program into the Arduino UNO controller.

7.3 ALGORITHM

Fig. 3: Flowchart of system working algorithm

Step-by-Step Algorithm

- 1) Start the system.
- 2) Initialize sensors and Arduino UNO.

- 3) Read MQ-2 sensor values.
- 4) Read flame sensor values.
- 5) Compare values with limits
- 6) If values are normal:
 - Continue monitoring
- 7) If smoke or flame is detected:
 - Active GSM Module.
 - Send SMS/call alert.
- 8) Repeat Monitoring continuously
- 9) Stop.

8. WORKING PRINCIPLE

The Purposed system works on the principle of environmental sensing and automatic GSM Module communication. The MQ-2 sensor continuously monitors smoke and harmful gases while the flame sensor detects infrared radiation produced by fire.

The Arduino UNO receives sensor values and compares them with predefined threshold limits programmed into the system. If abnormal conditions are detected, the controller activates the A7670C SIM Module.

The GSM module immediately sends SMS or call alerts to the user, informing them about the emergency situation. This fast communication helps users take immediate action and reduce damage.

The system provides reliable operation with low cost and easy implementation.

9. ADVANTAGES

- 1) Early fire and smoke detection.
- 2) Instant SMS/call alerts.
- 3) Low-cost.
- 4) Easy hardware setup.

- 5) Reliable operation.
- 6) Fast emergency communication.
- 7) Suitable for homes and industries.
- 8) Reduced human dependency.
- 9) Compact design.
- 10) Improved safety performance

10. APPLICATIONS

The proposed system can be used in:

- Residential homes
- Industrial plants
- Laboratories
- Warehouses
- Shopping Malls
- Hospitals
- Offices
- Education institutes
- Storage facilities

11. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The developed Smart fire detection and alert system successfully detect smoke and flame using MQ-2 and flame sensors respectively. During testing, the MQ-2 sensor effectively sensed smoke and gas leakage while the flame sensor accurately identified fire presence.

Fig. 4: Prototype of fire detection system setup

The Arduino UNO processed sensor values continuously and activated the GSM communication system whenever values exceeded safe limits.

The A7670C SIM module successfully transmitted emergency SMS and call alerts to users. The response time of system was fast enough to provide early warning during emergency situations.

The use of multiple sensor improved system accuracy and reduced false alarms. The proposed system demonstrated reliable operation with low power consumption and economical implementation.

11.1. Efficiency Discussion

The proposed system provides higher efficiency compared to traditional alarm systems because it combines multi-sensor monitoring with GSM communication.

11.2. Accuracy Discussion

The combination of MQ-2 and flame sensors improves detection accuracy and reduces false alert conditions.

Fig. 5: MQ-2 sensor smoke detection graph

11.3. Safety considerations

- Proper insulation should be used.
- Stable power supply is necessary.
- Sensor calibration should be performed regularly.
- System testing should be done periodically.

11.4. Limitations of the system

1. GSM network availability is required.
2. Sensor accuracy may vary in harsh environments.
3. Large industrial environments may require additional sensors.
4. Continuous power supply is necessary.

11. Future Scope

The Proposed system can be improved further using advanced technologies such as:

1. AI-based fire prediction.
2. Mobile application integration.
3. Automatic Sprinkler activation.
4. Cloud-based monitoring.
5. GPS tracking system.
6. Solar-powered operation.
7. Smart city integration.
8. Voice assistant support.
9. Camera-based monitoring.
10. Advanced wireless communication.

12. CONCLUSION

The smart Fire detection and Alert System using Arduino UNO and GSM communication provides an efficient, economical and reliable solution for fire safety applications. The proposed system successfully integrates MQ-2 smoke sensors, flame sensor, Arduino UNO controller, and A7670C SIM

module for real-time fire detection and emergency communication.

The system continuously monitors environmental conditions and sends instant SMS or call alerts whenever smoke or fire is detected. This quick response mechanism helps users take instant action and reduces the possibility of severe damage.

The use of multiple sensors improves detection accuracy and reliability. The project demonstrates how embedded systems and GSM communication can be effectively applied in modern safety systems. Future improvements such as AI integration, cloud monitoring, and automatic sprinkler systems can further improve the system performance.

Overall, the proposed project provides a practical and innovative solution for early fire detection and emergency alert generation, contributing to improved public safety and reduced property loss.

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